

Education and Peace its Relevance in World

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ABSTRACT

All nations of the world are directly or indirectly involved in a conflict, battle and war. All human being are suffering because of this. Human lives are lost in thousands and thousands. Human beings are in tension, stress and insecurity so this paper deals with peace, peace education, need of peace education, relevance of peace education in a modern world. Gandhi was a messenger of peace and Albert Einstein said in this regard that Generation to come would rarely believe that a man in flesh and blood like Gandhi ever walked upon this earth.

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Introduction:

Since war begins in the minds of men, it is in the minds of men of men that the defenses of peace must be constructed," But then the question, how the defenses of peace can be constructed in the minds of men?

- UNESCO

There is violence everywhere whether it is within human being or outside but all are in tension, frustrations and fear. As we are developing so we are becoming animals. Mahatma Gandhi was a great leader of Indian Independence. He was a peace lover and preacher of Non violence. In his own words my religion is based on truth and non violence. Truth is my God and Non violence is the means of realizing him. On his birth day we observe International Non violence day. It is his personality who made unique efforts to make the freedom struggle peacefully and it was so powerful that Gandhiji said that truth and non violence are more powerful than Atom bomb. Gandhi was a messenger of peace and Albert Einstein said in this regard that Generation to come would rarely believe that a man in flesh and blood like Gandhi ever walked upon this earth. Romin Rolland of France described Gandhi as "Jesus Christ without a cross". More than four hundred biographies on Gandhi have been written. There are innumerable thinkers and followers of Gandhi from all over the world like Nelson Mandela, Martin Luther King Jr. Vaclar Havel, Aung San Suu Kyi, Octavia Paz, and many more.

Peace is highly required in any civilized and cultured society, county and the world. If peace is lost everything is lost. It is necessary for individual well-being. It is an essential condition for both the individual's personal life and social relations. According to Mahatma Gandhi, 'I am convinced that a non – violent society can be built only on the foundation of harmony and cooperation, without which society is bound to remain violent. If we argue that this cannot be done it mean that a non violent society can never come into being. In that case our entire culture would be meaningless'.

Peace Education:

Peace Education is getting momentum in present time but before going to peace education it is needed to know the peace. Peace is generally considered absence of war and conflict or violence, it is also said that peace does not mean only absence of violence but also presence of calm, dignity, respect and freedom. Cambridge dictionary define peace as freedom from war and violence especially when people live and work together happily without disagreements. According to Page, a fundamental concern of peace education is a education which prevent to the suffering and wastage of warfare within the modern era. In view of Peace Education Working Group at UNICEF, peace education refers to the process of promoting the knowledge, skills

attitudes and values to prevent conflict and violence. Gandhiji concept of Satyagraha and Sarvodaya were based on the means of peace

Need of Peace Education:

In the words of Maria Montessori, "All education is for peace". It is said that, "Do not do to others what you would not like yourself; Never do to others what you would not like them to do to you". But the present human beings are in tension and frustration. Mrs Indra Gandhi once said that Freedom is indivisible, peace is indivisible and Economic prosperity is indivisible. We cannot imagine a sound society without peaceful environment. United Nations (UN) General Assembly in 1999 declared 2000-2010 by the UNESCO as the International Decade for Promotion of Culture of Peace and Non-violence for the Children of the World. The last five decades have witnessed several significant advocacies for education for peace. The UNESCO 6 recommendations on education for international understanding, peace, human rights, and fundamental freedoms (1974) and UNESCO's 1994 action plan for education for peace, human rights and democracy.

Wars and battles:

The twentieth century produced two of the worst wars in human history. Nuclear bomb, which was hailed as the ultimate weapon of mass destruction, contributed the climax to the trail of violence. Aggressive Human Nature, Socio-Economic and Political Inequalities, Denial of Human Rights, Religion, Ethnicity, Racism, Caste, ideology and because of many contemporary issues are the reasons of tension or conflict. All the wars, battles begin in anger and in the word of Benjamin Franklin "whatever begins in anger ends in shame". Unfortunately now in a days we see that war or battle begins in anger but not end in shame rather war begins in false ego and end in false pride, it seems we are returning to savage time. People on the name of nations, religions, castes, creeds, colors, geography kill people. Educated people have no courage, patience, kindness, or understanding of consequences. All are aggressive, tense and ready to fight or kill without knowing the right and wrong as Bertrand Russell said that, "war does not determine who is right- only who is left".

Sometime war begins only because of little difference on opinions and if opinion not settled then we start war and we left with murders that won and we pay heavy price to our leaders and society

Philosophy of Peace Education:

In a present time generally we people acquire knowledge under compulsion of getting good marks and finally job so it has no value in the words of Plato, "knowledge which is acquired under compulsion obtains no hold on mind". According to Gandhiji, by education I mean an all round drawing out of the best in child and man. Gandhiji's writings on education is compiled in two books, ' Basic Education (1951) and ' Towards New Education(1953). He believed that education is very broad concept and if it is implied in a better way, it can solve many issues of society and world. He also developed the concept of Buniyadi Shiksha (Basic Education or Nai Talim) in 1937 at Wardha based on the principle of non-violence. Gandhiji also stressed on head, hand and heart and also Aristotle said that, "Educating the mind without educating the heart is no education at all". Present education has nothing to do with heart.

Gandhiji was highly associated with peace education in the history of the world. Peace was central to Gandhiji's political, social and religious philosophy and he demonstrated to the world the supreme method of achieving world peace. Gandhi considered violence as the root cause of all evils. His method of non-violence identifies invariably with peace and truth. S.N Prasad says that "Gandhi's concept of education reflects more or less what we call today as peace education. The values he propounded reflect in his thought, speeches and in communication with others. The most fundamental principle of Gandhiji's philosophy of peace is "Ahimsa" or Non – violence which is the law of love, life and creation as opposed to violence or himsa, the cause of hatred, death and destruction; Gandhi considered non-violence as an indivisible, important and essential part of education and should serve as basic component guiding our day to day activities. Gandhiji advocated that the foundation of development of morality in a man should begin as early as in his childhood through moral and ethical education and

considered it as important and necessary for the all round development of personality in general to progress towards the path of peace. Gandhi always considered spiritual education as necessary parts of education. Gandhi advocated that religious studies in education would develop ethics and values of forbearance, tolerance and humanity. Since every religion preaches peace, it will help to inculcate it among the students in the very early age.

According to Gandhiji Peace is related to truth and non- violence. To face the challenges of the present time peace education is an essential aspect that would guide the man making to prevent violence and live in a harmonious society or world. Peace education is not just a concept that is coined in the academic world, it is a means to attain social justice, to live in accordance with moral rights and duties, and recognize one's relationship to all beings. Peace Education became a hope for a better world. Peace education is not only a part of study but it is a way of living. Efforts should be made to inculcate the values social, spiritual and moral. Values of harmony, respect and tolerance for better interpersonal relations should be promoted. Tolerance, acceptance of diversity and love are the basic law of life. It develops humanitarian and a peaceful society. History witness that struggle by the use of violence has no result at all, people have to cooperate people and negotiate problems at the individual as well as societal levels. Emphasis should be made to develop character education; self esteem and moral education are considered aspects of necessary in the individual reaching this personal inner potential and becoming a valued citizen for peaceful coexistence. Secondary Education Commission (1952-53) also identified character building as the defining goal of education,

The supreme end of the educative process should be the training of the character and personality of students in such a way that they will be able to realize their full potentialities and contribute to the well-being of the community". Respect of the diversity of traditions and practices practiced throughout the world should be highlighted while talking about the role of education in promoting peace. Cultural differences, identities of various groups and societies must be

recognized and respected.

Teacher as a Peace Builder:

It is generally said that what I teach is what I know and what I educate is what I am. A good teacher is always committed to prepare a good citizen and develop a peaceful society. Teacher always teach kindness, tolerance, love, truth, courage, cooperation and respect to all individual. Teacher promotes and develops values among students. A good teacher is ideal for his /her students. In a present society teacher require to play a major role to peace, prosperity and good will among people. It is a teacher who is really a builder of peace. Where ever there is tension, conflict and stress it is only teacher who can provide a good medicine to its pupil to develop a healthy personality. Teacher affect eternity his behavior and action impact upon students deeply. Teacher should also be a peace loving person so that he can teach peace because students learn peace values only if these are modeled by their teachers and elders. If there is a gap between teachers do and what they teach, students will imitate what is done. Teacher's speech, actions are judged by students very seriously. Therefore teacher play a big role actually teacher is a real peace builders in our society.

Suggestions:

Diplomacy, Political solution, Judicial, Negotiation, Good offices, Mediation, Inquiry, Conciliation, Economic fundamentals, Entrepreneurship and innovation, Democratic Institutions, Education, Health, Safety and Security, Governance, Personal Freedom, Social Capital. Intellectual and emotional development of the individuals, developing a sense of social responsibility and solidarity, observing the principles of equality and fraternity towards all, accepting and participating in free discussions, taking decisions on a rational basis, appreciating other's cultures, overcoming obstacles are necessary to promote peace. Educational curriculum should be constructed in such a way to develop the values, respect each other, understand culture, religion of one another, value the life of human being, and follow the rules and regulations of wars and battles.

Conclusion:

It may be concluded in the word of Dwight D. Eisenhower, “One day. The people of the world will want peace so much that governments are going to have to get out of their way and then have it.” At present scenario, the situation within individual and in a society is very tense and critical which make Gandhi Philosophy of Peace Education highly relevant. Everywhere there is a conflict, battle, war, negative competition and frustration. Human beings are tortured and killed by human being. Education seems that it has lost its relevance in making or preparing a good human being who know himself or herself, who can work for humanity and who know the purpose of life. In this situation peace education is considered as the highly relevant and concept of peace, truth and non violence is compulsorily required to be included in everywhere in the curriculum of Education as a peace education and students should be taught values and peace education to develop a harmonious and peaceful society, country and the world.

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